

Data management plan for project "Flourishing for friendship: conceptual research on the interplay between deep friendship and moral development"

Version 3

Description

In 2017-2024, postdoctoral research and 2 LCS projects investigated the understanding and needs of moral education in the Latvian education system. The goals of the fundamental research proposed in this project are (1) to develop a new theory of friendship as the goal of moral development based on transcendental anthropology; and (2) to establish the theoretical foundations for applying this moral theory to empirical research and moral education.

The research questions addressed are: What is the conceptual relationship between moral growth and deep friendship in scientific literature? What is the contribution of transcendental anthropology in this field? How to design empirical research about the relationship between friendship and moral growth? How can virtue-based friendship be developed in school practice? Research methods include AI-based conceptual literature review, focus group discussions and expert seminars.

Project results: 2 scientific publications submitted (to a scientific journal and in conference proceedings indexed in WoS/SCOPUS), and 1 application for national or international R&I support mechanisms. The result will be presented in 3 scientific conferences (1 in Latvia, 2 in Europe) and in a book in Latvian of top 10 moral education studies. They will set the theoretical foundations for further empirical research about youngsters' understandings of virtue-based friendship and its promotion at school. The project will enhance UL competitiveness.

Project financed by the Recovery and resilience Facility project "Internal and external consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No 5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007), grant "Flourishing for friendship: conceptual research on the interplay between deep friendship and moral development" No. LU-BA-ZG-2024/1-0028

Funder

European Commission | | EC

Grant

Recovery and resilience Facility project "Internal and external consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/24/I/CFLA/007)

Researchers

Manuel Joaquín Fernández González (0000-0002-7088-672X)

Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data management plan for project "Flourishing for friendship: conceptual research on the interplay between deep friendship and moral development"

Description:

In 2017-2024, postdoctoral research and 2 LCS projects investigated the understanding and needs of moral education in the Latvian education system. The goals of the fundamental research proposed in this project are (1) to develop a new theory of friendship as the goal of moral development based on transcendental anthropology; and (2) to establish the theoretical foundations for applying this moral theory to empirical research and moral education.

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Organizations:

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Contact: Fernandez Gonzalez Manuel Joaquin (manuels.fernandezs@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

Grants: Recovery and resilience Facility project "Internal and external consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/24/I/CFLA/007)

Project: Flourishing for friendship: conceptual research on the interplay between deep friendship and moral development (Nr. LU-BA-ZG-2024/1-0028)

3. License

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4. Templates

Descriptions

List of scientific literature on friendship and moral growth

Conceptual literature review on friendship and moral growth (in English, Spanish, French and Latvian)

1. Objectives and scope definition. The objectives of the review will focus on the interplay between friendships and moral development. This will establish the framework for identifying relevant theoretical and empirical works.

2. Research question. The investigation will be guided by the first research question of the project – RQ1 How are the constructs of moral growth and deep friendship theorized in scientific literature? What is the conceptual relationship between moral growth and deep friendship in scientific literature?

3. Keyword identification and systematic searches. Critical keywords such as "moral development", "friendships", "virtue growth" will be selected. Systematic searches will be conducted across major academic databases (WoS, SCOPUS, Google Scholar etc.) for ensuring a comprehensive and reproducible search process.

4. Literature screening and selection. Titles and abstracts will be initially screened to identify articles discussing the interplay between moral growth and friendship. Full texts will be assessed against stringent inclusion criteria to ensure relevance and quality.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

(1) to develop a new theory of friendship as the goal of moral development based on transcendental anthropology; and (2) to establish the theoretical foundations for applying this moral theory to empirical research and moral education.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Other

Textual list of scientific literature

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT

- PDF

- XLS

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

50

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No similar data available

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Researchers in the field of moral education

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

Journal of publication, Open access, year of publication

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Microsoft Excel, Word, pdf reader

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2026-03-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2029-03-31

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Manuel Joaquín Fernández González (0000-0002-7088-672X)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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